

Some New Type of Contraction and Common Fixed-Point Theorem in Fuzzy Metric Space

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Abstract- The main objective of writing this research paper is to prove the Common Fixed Point Theorem in Fuzzy Metric Space with a new type of contraction.

Keywords: Compatibility mappings, Common fixed point, Fuzzy metric space, Self-mapping etc.

I. INTRODUCTION

The [5] S. Banach fixed point theorem is important as a source of existence and uniqueness of theorem in different branches of analysis. In this way the theorem provides an impressive illustration of the unifying power of functional analytic method and of the usefulness of fixed point theorems in analysis.

The [5] S. Banach fixed point theorem or contraction principle concerns certain mappings of a complete metric space into itself. It states conditions sufficient for the existence and uniqueness of a fixed point. The theorem also gives an iterative process by which we can obtain approximations to the fixed point and error bounds etc. Compatibility is a powerful tool for generalization of [5] S. Banach contraction principle recently many authors generalized [5] S. Banach principle, use of commutatively and compatibility concept. Present paper introduce new type of contraction and proved common fixed point theorem in fuzzy metrics space.

The concept of fuzzy sets was introduced initially by Zadeh. Since then, it was developed extensively by many authors and used in various fields. Specially [7, 8] introduce the concept of fuzzy metric spaces in different ways.

In present paper we use in [8], George and Veeramani modified the concept of fuzzy metric space which introduced by Kromosil and Michalek.

Further Jungck [1] introduced compatibility in metric space. He proved common fixed point theorems in to metric spaces.

Preliminary definition:

Definition: 1. A binary operation $*$: $[0, 1] \times [0, 1] \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is called a continuous t-norm if $([0, 1], *)$ is abelian topological monoid with 1 such that $a * b \leq c * d$, whenever $a \leq c, b \leq d$ for all a, b, c, d in $[0, 1]$.

Definition:2. the 3-tuple $(X, F, *)$ is called a fuzzy metric space if X is an arbitrary set, $*$ is a continuous t-norm and M is a fuzzy set on $X \times X \times (0, \infty)$ satisfying the following conditions:

$$(I) \quad F(x, y, t) > 0,$$

$$(II) \quad F(x, y, t) = 1 \text{ if and only if } x = y,$$

$$(III) \quad F(x, y, t) = F(y, x, t),$$

$$(IV) \quad F(x, y, t) * F(y, z, s) \leq F(x, z, t + s),$$

$$(V) \quad F(x, y, \cdot): (0, \infty) \rightarrow$$

$[0, 1]$ is continuous,

For all x, y, z in X and $t, s > 0$.

COMPATIBILITY (1) [1]: Let A and B be a pair of self-maps of a complete fuzzy metric space $(X, M, *)$. Then A and B are said to be compatible if $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} F(ABx_n, BAx_n, t) = 1$, for all $t > 0$ whenever $\{x_n\}$ is a sequence in X such that $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} Ax_n = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} Bx_n = z$ for some $z \in X$.

Main Result

Theorem (1): Let $(X, F, *)$ be a complete fuzzy metric space and let $f, g, A, B, C, D, H, I, J, K, L, M, N, P, Q, R, S, T, U, V, \delta, \beta$ be self mappings of X such that following conditions are satisfying:

$$(I) \quad f \subset A, f \subset C, f \subset H, f \subset J, f \subset L, f \subset N, f \subset Q, f \subset S, f \subset U, f \subset \delta, \\ g \subset B, g \subset D, g \subset I, g \subset K, g \subset M, g \subset P, g \subset R, g \subset T, g \subset V, g \subset \beta$$

(II) $f, g, A, B, C, D, H, I, J, K, L, M, N, P, Q, R, S, T, U, V, \delta, \beta$ are continuous,

(III) Pairs are $[f, B], [f, D], [f, I], [f, K], [f, M], [f, P], [f, R], [f, T], [f, V], [f, \beta]$ and $[g, A], [g, C], [g, H], [g, J], [g, L],$

$[g, N], [g, Q], [g, S], [g, U], [g, \delta]$ compatible,

(IV) $F(fx, gy, \alpha t) \geq \max \{F(Ax, By, t), F(Cx, Dy, t), F(Hx, Iy, t), F(Jx, Ky, t), F(Lx, My, t), F(Nx, Py, t), F(Qx, Ry, t), F(Sx, Ty, t), F(Ux, Vy, t), F(\delta x, \beta y, t)\}$

Where $0 < \alpha < 1$ and every $x, y \in X, t > 0$. Then $f, g, A, B, C, D, H, I, J, K, L, M, N, P, Q, R, S, T, U, V, \delta, \beta$ have a unique common fixed point in X .

Proof: Let $x_0 \in X$ arbitrary and $f(X) \subset A(X)$ exist $x_1 \in X$ such that $fx_0 = Ax_1$ and for this, $x_1 \in X$ and $g(X) \subset B(X)$ there exist $x_2 \in X$ such that $gx_1 = Bx_2$ and for this, $x_2 \in X$ and $f(X) \subset C(X)$ there exist $x_3 \in X$ such that $fx_2 = Cx_3$ and for this, $x_3 \in X$ and $g(X) \subset D(X)$ there exist $x_4 \in X$ such that $gx_3 = Dx_4$ and for this, $x_4 \in X$ and $f(X) \subset H(X)$ there exist $x_5 \in X$ such that $fx_4 = Hx_5$ and for this, $x_5 \in X$ and $g(X) \subset I(X)$ there exist $x_6 \in X$ such that $gx_5 = Ix_6$ and for this, $x_6 \in X$ and $f(X) \subset J(X)$ there exist $x_7 \in X$ such that $fx_6 = Jx_7$ and for this, $x_7 \in X$ and $g(X) \subset K(X)$ there exist $x_8 \in X$ such that $gx_7 = Kx_8$ and for this, $x_8 \in X$ and $f(X) \subset L(X)$ there exist $x_9 \in X$ such that $fx_8 = Lx_9$ and for this, $x_9 \in X$ and $g(X) \subset M(X)$ there exist $x_{10} \in X$ such that $gx_9 = Mx_{10}$ and for this, $x_{10} \in X$ and $f(X) \subset N(X)$ there exist $x_{11} \in X$ such that $fx_{10} = Nx_{11}$ and for this, $x_{11} \in X$ and $g(X) \subset P(X)$ there exist $x_{12} \in X$ such that $gx_{11} = Px_{12}$ and for this, $x_{12} \in X$ and $f(X) \subset Q(X)$ there exist $x_{13} \in X$ such that $fx_{12} = Qx_{13}$ and for this, $x_{13} \in X$ and $g(X) \subset R(X)$ there exist $x_{14} \in X$ such that $gx_{13} = Rx_{14}$ and for this, $x_{14} \in X$ and $f(X) \subset S(X)$ there exist $x_{15} \in X$ such that $fx_{14} = Sx_{15}$ and for this, $x_{15} \in X$ and $g(X) \subset T(X)$ there exist $x_{16} \in X$ such that $gx_{15} = Tx_{16}$ and for this, $x_{16} \in X$ and $f(X) \subset U(X)$ there exist $x_{17} \in X$ such that $fx_{16} = Ux_{17}$ and for this, $x_{17} \in X$ and $g(X) \subset V(X)$ there exist $x_{18} \in X$ such that $gx_{17} = Vx_{18}$ and for this, $x_{18} \in X$ and $f(X) \subset \delta(X)$ there exist $x_{19} \in X$ such that $fx_{18} = \delta x_{19}$ and for this, $x_{19} \in X$ and $g(X) \subset \beta(X)$ there exist $x_{20} \in X$ such

h that $gx_{19} = \beta x_{20}$ In simple induction we construct a sequence $\{y_n\}$ in X as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} fx_{20n-20} &= Ax_{20n-19} = y_{20n-19} & , gx_{20n-19} &= \\ Bx_{20n-18} &= y_{20n-18} & , fx_{20n-18} &= Cx_{20n-17} = \\ y_{20n-17} & , gx_{20n-17} &= Dx_{20n-16} = y_{20n-16} & , fx_{20n-16} = \\ Hx_{20n-15} &= y_{20n-15} & , gx_{20n-15} &= Ix_{20n-14} = \\ y_{20n-14} & , fx_{20n-14} &= Jx_{20n-13} = y_{20n-13} & , gx_{20n-13} = \\ Kx_{20n-12} &= y_{20n-12} & , fx_{20n-12} &= Lx_{20n-11} = \\ y_{20n-11} & , gx_{20n-11} &= Mx_{20n-10} = y_{20n-10} & , \\ fx_{20n-10} &= Nx_{20n-9} = y_{20n-9} & , gx_{20n-9} &= \\ Px_{20n-8} &= y_{20n-8} & , fx_{20n-8} &= Qx_{20n-7} = \\ y_{20n-7} & , gx_{20n-7} &= Rx_{20n-6} = y_{20n-6} & , fx_{20n-6} = \\ Sx_{20n-5} &= y_{20n-5} & , gx_{20n-5} &= Tx_{20n-4} = y_{20n-4} \\ , fx_{20n-4} &= Ux_{20n-3} = y_{20n-3} & , gx_{20n-3} &= Vx_{20n-2} = \\ y_{20n-2} & & , fx_{20n-2} &= \delta x_{20n-1} = y_{20n-1} & , gx_{20n-1} = \\ \beta x_{20n} &= y_{20n} & , \text{for } n = 1, 2, 3, \dots \end{aligned}$$

By Use of condition (iv) with $x = x_{20n}$ and $y = x_{20n+1}$

$$\begin{aligned} F(y_{20n+1}, y_{20n+2}, \alpha t) &= F(fx_{20n}, gx_{20n+1}, \alpha t) \geq \\ \max \{ & F(Ax_{20n}, Bx_{20n+1}, t), F(Cx_{20n}, Dx_{20n+1}, t), \\ & F(Hx_{20n}, Ix_{20n+1}, t), F(Jx_{20n}, Kx_{20n+1}, t), \\ & F(Lx_{20n}, Mx_{20n+1}, t), F(Nx_{20n}, Px_{20n+1}, t), \\ & F(Qx_{20n}, Rx_{20n+1}, t), \\ & F(Sx_{20n}, Tx_{20n+1}, t), F(Ux_{20n}, Vx_{20n+1}, t), F(\delta x_{20n}, \beta x_{20n+1}, t) \\ & \} \\ & \geq F(y_{20n}, y_{20n+1}, \alpha t) \end{aligned}$$

$$F(y_{20n+1}, y_{20n+2}, \alpha t) \geq F(y_{20n}, y_{20n+1}, t) \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

Similarly we get,

$$F(y_{20n+2}, y_{20n+3}, \alpha t) \geq F(y_{20n+1}, y_{20n+2}, t) \dots \dots \dots (2)$$

By equation (1) and (2) we have

$$F(y_{n+1}, y_{n+2}, \alpha t) \geq F(y_n, y_{n+1}, t) \dots \dots \dots (3)$$

In simple induction

$$F(y_n, y_{n+1}, \alpha t) \geq F(y_n, y_{n-1}, \frac{t}{\alpha^n}) \geq F(y_{n-2}, y_{n-1}, \frac{t}{\alpha^n}) \geq \dots \geq F(y_1, y_2, \frac{t}{\alpha^n}) \rightarrow 1$$

as $n \rightarrow \infty$

So $F(y_n, y_{n+1}, \alpha t) \rightarrow 1$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$, for any $t > 0$.
Let each $\epsilon > 0$ and $t > 0$, we can choose $n_0 \in \mathbf{N}$ such that $F(y_n, y_{n+1}, \alpha t) \rightarrow > 1 - \epsilon$ all $n > n_0$.

Let $m, n \in \mathbb{N}$ suppose $m \geq n$. Thus we have

$$F(y_n, y_m, \alpha t) \geq F\left(y_n, y_{n+1}, \frac{t}{m-n}\right) * F\left(y_{n+1}, y_{n+2}, \frac{t}{m-n}\right) * \dots * F\left(y_{m-1}, y_m, \frac{t}{m-n}\right) > (1-\epsilon) * (1-\epsilon) * (1-\epsilon) * \dots * (1-\epsilon) \{m-n \text{ time}\} \geq 1-\epsilon$$

Hence $\{y_n\}$ is a Cauchy sequence in X . $(X, F, *)$ is complete fuzzy metric space, $\{y_n\}$ converges some $z \in X$, and so

$$\{fx_{20n-20}\}, \{gx_{20n-19}\}, \{Ax_{20n-18}\}, \{Bx_{20n-17}\}, \{Cx_{20n-16}\}, \{Dx_{20n-15}\}, \{Hx_{20n-14}\}, \{Ix_{20n-13}\}, \{Jx_{20n-12}\}, \{Kx_{20n-11}\}, \{Lx_{20n-10}\}, \{Mx_{20n-9}\}, \{Nx_{20n-8}\}, \{Px_{20n-7}\}, \{Qx_{20n-6}\}, \{Rx_{20n-5}\}, \{Sx_{20n-4}\}, \{Tx_{20n-3}\}, \{Ux_{20n-3}\}, \{Vx_{20n-2}\}, \{\delta x_{20n-1}\}, \{\beta x_{20n}\} \text{ also converges } \rightarrow z.$$

Case I:

Let $x = Bx_{20n-17}$ and $y = Ax_{20n-18}$, (iii)
 $fBx_{20n-17}, ABx_{20n-17}, CBx_{20n-17}, HBx_{20n-17}, JBx_{20n-17}, LBx_{20n-17}, NBx_{20n-17}, QBx_{20n-17}, SBx_{20n-17}, UBx_{20n-17} \rightarrow Bz,$
 $gAx_{20n-18}, BAx_{20n-18}, DAx_{20n-18}, IAx_{20n-18}, KAx_{20n-18}, MAx_{20n-18}, PAX_{20n-18}, RAX_{20n-18}, TAX_{20n-18}, VAX_{20n-18} \rightarrow Az$

$$F(fBx_{20n-17}, gAx_{20n-18}, \alpha t) \geq \max. \{F(ABx_{20n-17}, BAx_{20n-18}, t), F(CBx_{20n-17}, DAx_{20n-18}, t), F(HBx_{20n-17}, IAx_{20n-18}, t), F(JBx_{20n-17}, KAx_{20n-18}, t), F(LBx_{20n-17}, MAx_{20n-18}, t), F(NBx_{20n-17}, PAX_{20n-18}, t), F(QBx_{20n-17}, RAX_{20n-18}, t), F(SBx_{20n-17}, TAX_{20n-18}, t), F(UBx_{20n-17}, VAX_{20n-18}, t)\} \text{ as } n \rightarrow \infty$$

$$F(Bz, Az, \alpha t) \geq \max. \{F(Bz, Az, t), F(Bz, Az, t)\} \text{ as } n \rightarrow \infty$$

$$F(Bz, Az, \alpha t) \geq F(Bz, Az, t) \text{ . Hence } Bz = Az.$$

$$F(Bz, z, \alpha t) \geq F(Bz, z, t) \text{ . Such that } Bz = Az = z \text{ . (4)}$$

Let $x = Dx_{20n-16}$ and $y = Cx_{20n-17}$, (iii)
 $fDx_{20n-16}, ADx_{20n-16}, CDx_{20n-16}, HDx_{20n-16}, JDx_{20n-16}, LDx_{20n-16}$

$$NDx_{20n-16}, QDx_{20n-16}, SDx_{20n-16}, UDx_{20n-16}, \delta Dx_{20n-16} \rightarrow Dz,$$

$$gCx_{20n-17}, BCx_{20n-17}, DCx_{20n-17}, ICx_{20n-17}, KCx_{20n-17}, MCx_{20n-17}, PCx_{20n-17}, RCx_{20n-17}, TCx_{20n-17}, VCx_{20n-17}, \beta Cx_{20n-17} \rightarrow Cz$$

$$F(fDx_{20n-16}, gCx_{20n-17}, \alpha t) \geq \max. \{F(ADx_{20n-16}, BCx_{20n-17}, t), F(CDx_{20n-16}, DCx_{20n-17}, t), F(HDx_{20n-16}, ICx_{20n-17}, t), F(JDx_{20n-16}, KCx_{20n-17}, t), F(LDx_{20n-16}, MCx_{20n-17}, t), F(NDx_{20n-16}, PCx_{20n-17}, t), F(QDx_{20n-16}, RCx_{20n-17}, t), (SDx_{20n-16}, TCx_{20n-17}, t), F(UDx_{20n-16}, VCx_{20n-17}, t), F(\delta Dx_{20n-16}, \beta Cx_{20n-17}, t)\} \text{ as } n \rightarrow \infty$$

$$F(Dz, Cz, \alpha t) \geq \max. \{F(Dz, Cz, t), F(Dz, Cz, t)\} \text{ as } n \rightarrow \infty$$

$$F(Dz, Cz, \alpha t) \geq F(Dz, Cz, t) \text{ . Hence } Dz = Cz \text{ .}$$

$$F(Dz, z, \alpha t) \geq F(Dz, z, t) \text{ . Such that } Dz = Cz = z \text{ . (5)}$$

Let $x = Ix_{20n-14}$ and $y = Hx_{20n-15}$, (iii) and (iv) we have

$$fIx_{18n-12}, AIx_{20n-14}, CIx_{20n-14}, HIx_{20n-14}, JIx_{20n-14}, LIx_{20n-14}, NIX_{20n-14}, QIX_{20n-14}, SIX_{20n-14}, UIx_{20n-14}, \delta Ix_{20n-14} \rightarrow Iz,$$

$$gHx_{20n-15}, BHx_{20n-15}, DHx_{20n-15}, IHx_{20n-15}, KHx_{20n-15}, MHx_{20n-15}, PHx_{20n-15}, RHx_{20n-15}, THx_{20n-15}, VHx_{20n-15}, \beta Hx_{20n-15} \rightarrow Hz$$

$$F(fIx_{20n-14}, gHx_{20n-15}, \alpha t) \geq \max. \{F(AIx_{20n-14}, BHx_{20n-15}, t), F(CIx_{20n-14}, DHx_{20n-15}, t), F(HIx_{20n-14}, IHx_{20n-15}, t), F(JIx_{20n-14}, KHx_{20n-15}, t), F(LIx_{20n-14}, MHx_{20n-15}, t), F(NIX_{20n-14}, PHx_{20n-15}, t), F(QIX_{20n-14}, RHx_{20n-15}, t), (SIX_{20n-14}, THx_{20n-15}, t), F(UIx_{20n-14}, VHx_{20n-15}, t), F(\delta Ix_{20n-14}, \beta Hx_{20n-15}, t)\} \text{ as } n \rightarrow \infty$$

$$F(Iz, Hz, \alpha t) \geq \max. \{F(Iz, Hz, t), F(Iz, Hz, t)\} \text{ as } n \rightarrow \infty$$

$$F(Iz, Hz, \alpha t) \geq F(Iz, Hz, t) \text{ . Hence } Iz = Hz \text{ . } F(Iz, z, \alpha t) \geq F(Iz, z, t)$$

$Iz = z$. Such that $Iz = Hz = z$. (6)

Let $x = Kx_{20n-12}$ and

$y = Jx_{20n-13}$,

(iii) and (iv) we have

$fKx_{20n-12}, AKx_{20n-12}, CKx_{20n-12}, HKx_{20n-12},$

$JKx_{20n-12}, LKx_{20n-12}$

$NKx_{20n-12}, QKx_{20n-12}, SKx_{20n-12}, UKx_{20n-12}$

$\delta Kx_{20n-12} \rightarrow Kz,$

$gJx_{20n-13}, BJx_{20n-13}, DJx_{20n-13}, IJx_{20n-13}, KJx_{20n-13}, F(Mz, z, \alpha t) \geq F(Mz, z, t)$

MJx_{20n-13}

$PJx_{20n-13}, RJx_{20n-13}, TJx_{20n-13}, VJx_{20n-13}$

$\beta Jx_{20n-13} \rightarrow Jz$

$F(fKx_{20n-12}, gJx_{20n-13}, \alpha t) \geq$

$\max. \{ FM(AKx_{20n-12}, BJx_{20n-13}, t),$

$F(CKx_{20n-12}, DJx_{20n-13}, t),$

$F(HKx_{20n-12}, IJx_{20n-13}, t),$

$F(JKx_{20n-12}, KJx_{20n-13}, t),$

$F(LKx_{20n-12}, MJx_{20n-13}, t),$

$F(NKx_{20n-12}, PJx_{20n-13}, t),$

$F(QKx_{20n-12}, RJx_{20n-13}, t),$

$(SKx_{20n-12}, TJx_{20n-13}, t), F(UKx_{20n-12}, VJx_{20n-13}, t)$

$, F(\delta Kx_{20n-12}, \beta Jx_{20n-13}, t) \}$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$

$F(Kz, Jz, \alpha t) \geq$

$\max. \{ F(Kz, Jz, t), F(Kz, Jz, t), F(Kz, Jz, t), F(Kz, Jz, t),$

$F(Mz, Jz, t),$

$F(Kz, Hz, t), F(Kz, Hz, t), F(Kz, Hz, t), F(Kz, Hz, t), F(PNz, Nz, t), RNx_{20n-9}, TNx_{20n-9}, VNx_{20n-9}, \beta Nz_{20n-9}$

$\}$

$M(Kz, Jz, \alpha t) \geq M(Kz, Jz, t)$. Hence

$Kz = Jz$. $F(Kz, z, \alpha t) \geq F(Kz, z, t)$

$Kz = z$. Such that $Kz = Jz = z$. (7)

Let $x = Mx_{20n-10}$, and $y = Lx_{20n-11}$,

(iii) and (iv) we have

$fMx_{18n-8}, AMx_{20n-10}, CMx_{20n-10}, HMx_{20n-10},$

$JMx_{20n-10}, LMx_{20n-10}$

$NMx_{20n-10}, QMx_{20n-10}, SMx_{20n-10}, UMx_{20n-10},$

$\delta Mx_{20n-10} \rightarrow Mz,$

$gLx_{20n-11}, BLx_{20n-11}, DLx_{20n-11}, ILx_{20n-11},$

$KLx_{20n-11}, MLx_{20n-11}$

$PLx_{20n-11}, RLx_{20n-11}, TLx_{20n-11}, VLx_{20n-11}, \beta Lx_{20n-11}$

$\rightarrow Lz$

$F(fMx_{20n-10}, gLx_{20n-11}, \alpha t) \geq$

$\max. \{ F(AMx_{20n-10}, BLx_{20n-11}, t),$

$F(CMx_{20n-10}, DLx_{20n-11}, t),$

$F(HMx_{20n-10}, ILx_{20n-11}, t),$

$F(JMx_{20n-10}, KLx_{20n-11}, t),$

$F(LMx_{20n-10}, MLx_{20n-11}, t),$

$F(NMx_{20n-10}, PLx_{20n-11}, t),$

$F(QMx_{20n-10}, RLx_{20n-11}, t),$

$(SMx_{20n-10}, TLx_{20n-11}, t), F(UMx_{20n-10}, VLx_{20n-11}, t)$

$, F(\delta Mx_{20n-10}, \beta Lx_{20n-11}, t) \}$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$

$F(Mz, Lz, \alpha t) \geq$

$\max. \{ F(Mz, Lz, t), F(Mz, Lz, t), F(Mz, Lz, t), F(Mz, Lz, t),$

$F(Mz, Lz, t),$

$F(Mz, Lz, t), F(Mz, Lz, t), F(Mz, Lz, t), F(Mz, Lz, t)$

$, F(Mz, Lz, t) \}$

$F(Mz, Lz, \alpha t) \geq F(Mz, Lz, t)$

$Mz = Lz$.

$Mz = z$. Such that $Mz = Lz = z$. (8)

Let $x = Px_{20n-8}$, and $y = Nx_{20n-9}$,

(iii) and (iv) we have

$fPx_{18n-6}, APx_{20n-8}, CPx_{20n-8}, HPx_{20n-8}, JPx_{20n-8},$

LPx_{20n-8}

$NPx_{20n-8}, QPx_{20n-8}, SPx_{20n-8}, UPx_{20n-8}, \delta Px_{20n-8}$

$\rightarrow Pz,$

$gNx_{20n-9}, BNx_{20n-9}, DNx_{20n-9}, INx_{20n-9}, KNx_{20n-9},$

MNx_{20n-9}

$F(PNz, Nz, t), RNx_{20n-9}, TNx_{20n-9}, VNx_{20n-9}, \beta Nz_{20n-9}$

$\rightarrow Nz$

$F(fPx_{20n-8}, gNx_{20n-9}, \alpha t) \geq$

$\max. \{ F(APx_{20n-8}, BNx_{20n-9}, t),$

$F(CPx_{20n-8}, DNx_{20n-9}, t),$

$M(HPx_{20n-8}, INx_{20n-9}, t),$

$M(JPx_{20n-8}, KNx_{20n-9}, t),$

$M(LPx_{20n-8}, MNx_{20n-9}, t),$

$F(NPx_{20n-8}, PNx_{20n-9}, t), F(QPx_{20n-8}, RNx_{20n-9}, t)$

$, (SPx_{20n-8}, TNx_{20n-9}, t), F(UPx_{20n-8}, VNx_{20n-9}, t)$

$, F(\delta Px_{20n-8}, \beta Nz_{20n-9}, t) \}$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$

$F(Pz, Nz, \alpha t) \geq$

$\max. \{ F(Pz, Nz, t), F(Pz, Nz, t), F(Pz, Nz, t), F(Pz, Nz, t),$

$F(Pz, Nz, t),$

$F(Pz, Nz, t), F(Pz, Nz, t), F(Pz, Nz, t), F(Pz, Nz, t),$

$, F(Pz, Nz, t) \}$

$F(Pz, Nz, \alpha t) \geq F(Pz, Nz, t)$

$Pz = Nz$.

$F(Pz, z, \alpha t) \geq F(Pz, z, t)$

$Pz = z$. Such that $Pz = Nz = z$. (9)

Let $x = Rx_{20n-6}$, and $y = Qx_{20n-7}$,

(iii) and (iv) we have

$fRx_{18n-4}, ARx_{20n-6}, CRx_{20n-6}, HRx_{20n-6}, JRx_{20n-6},$
 LRx_{20n-6}

$NRx_{20n-6}, QRx_{20n-6}, SRx_{20n-6}, URx_{20n-6}$,

$\delta Rx_{20n-6} \rightarrow Rz$,

$gQx_{20n-7}, BQx_{20n-7}, DQx_{20n-7}, IQx_{20n-7}, KQx_{20n-7}, MQx_{20n-7}$

$PQx_{20n-7}, RQx_{20n-7}, TQx_{20n-7}, VQx_{20n-7}, \beta Qx_{20n-7}$
 $\rightarrow Qz$

$F(fRx_{20n-6}, gQx_{20n-7}, \alpha t) \geq$

$\max. \{ F(ARx_{20n-6}, BQx_{20n-7}, t),$

$F(CRx_{20n-6}, DQx_{20n-7}, t),$

$F(HRx_{20n-6}, IQx_{20n-7}, t), F(JRx_{18n-4}, KQx_{20n-7}, t),$

$F(LRx_{20n-6}, MQx_{20n-7}, t), F(NRx_{20n-6}, PQx_{20n-7}, t),$

$F(QRx_{20n-6}, RQx_{20n-7}, t),$

$(SRx_{20n-6}, TQx_{20n-7}, t), F(URx_{20n-6}, VQx_{20n-7}, t), F(\delta Rx_{20n-6}, \beta Qx_{20n-7}, t)$

$\}$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$

$F(Rz, Qz, \alpha t) \geq$

$\max. \{ F(Rz, Qz, t), F(Rz, Qz, t), F(Rz, Qz, t), F(Rz, Qz, t),$

$F(Rz, Qz, t),$

$F(Rz, Qz, t), F(Rz, Qz, t), F(Rz, Qz, t), F(Rz, Qz, t)$

$, F(Rz, Qz, t)\}$

$F(Rz, Qz, \alpha t) \geq F(Rz, Qz, t)$

$Rz = Qz$.

$M(Rz, z, \alpha t) \geq M(Rz, z, t)$

$Rz = z$. such that $Rz = Qz = z$. (10)

Let $x = Tx_{20n-4}$, and $y = Sx_{20n-5}$,

(iii) and (iv) we have

$fTx_{20n-4}, ATx_{20n-4}, CTx_{20n-4}, HTx_{20n-4},$

JTx_{20n-4}, LTx_{20n-4}

$NTx_{20n-4}, QTx_{20n-4}, STx_{20n-4}, UTx_{20n-4}, \delta Tx_{20n-4}$

$\rightarrow Tz$,

$gSx_{20n-5}, BSx_{20n-5}, DSx_{20n-5}, ISx_{20n-5}, KSx_{20n-5},$

MSx_{20n-5}

$PSx_{20n-5}, RSx_{20n-5}, TSx_{20n-5}, VSx_{20n-5}$

$, \beta Sx_{20n-5} \rightarrow Sz$

$F(fVx_{18n}, gSx_{20n-5}, \alpha t) \geq$

$\max. \{ F(AVx_{18n}, BSx_{20n-5}, t),$

$F(CVx_{18n}, DSx_{20n-5}, t),$

$F(HVx_{18n}, ISx_{20n-5}, t), F(JVx_{18n}, KSx_{20n-5}, t),$

$F(LVx_{18n}, MSx_{20n-5}, t), F(NVx_{18n}, PSx_{20n-5}, t),$

$F(QVx_{18n}, RSx_{20n-5}, t),$

$(SVx_{18n}, TSx_{20n-5}, t), F(UVx_{18n}, VSx_{20n-5}, t),$

$F(\delta Vx_{18n}, \beta Sx_{20n-5}, t) \}$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$

$F(Tz, Sz, \alpha t) \geq$

$\max. \{ F(Tz, Sz, t), F(Tz, Sz, t), F(Tz, Sz, t), F(Tz, Sz, t),$

$F(Tz, Sz, t),$

$F(Tz, Sz, t), F(Tz, Sz, t), F(Tz, Sz, t), F(Tz, Sz, t),$

$F(Tz, Sz, t)\}$

$F(Tz, Sz, \alpha t) \geq F(Tz, Sz, t)$

$Tz = Sz$.

$F(Tz, z, \alpha t) \geq F(Tz, z, t)$

$Tz = z$. Such that $Tz = Sz = z$. (11)

Let $x = Vx_{20n-2}$, and $y = Ux_{20n-3}$,

(iii) and (iv) we have

$fVx_{20n-2}, AVx_{20n-2}, CVx_{20n-2}, HVx_{20n-2}, JVx_{20n-2},$

LVx_{20n-2}

$NVx_{20n-2}, QVx_{20n-2}, SVx_{20n-2}, UVx_{20n-2}$,

$\delta Vx_{20n-2} \rightarrow Vz$,

$gUx_{20n-3}, BUx_{20n-3}, DUx_{20n-3}, IUx_{20n-3}, KUx_{20n-3},$

MUx_{20n-3}

$PUx_{20n-3}, RUx_{20n-3}, TUx_{20n-3}, VUx_{20n-3}$

$, \beta Ux_{20n-3} \rightarrow Uz$

$F(fVx_{20n-2}, gUx_{20n-3}, \alpha t) \geq$

$\max. \{ F(AVx_{20n-2}, BUx_{20n-3}, t),$

$F(CVx_{20n-2}, DUx_{20n-3}, t),$

$F(HVx_{20n-2}, IUx_{20n-3}, t), F(JVx_{20n-2}, KUx_{20n-3}, t),$

$F(LVx_{20n-2}, MUx_{20n-3}, t), F(NVx_{20n-2}, PUx_{20n-3}, t),$

$F(QVx_{20n-2}, RUx_{20n-3}, t),$

$(SVx_{20n-2}, TUx_{20n-3}, t), F(UVx_{20n-2}, VUx_{20n-3}, t),$

$F(\delta Vx_{20n-2}, \beta Ux_{20n-3}, t) \}$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$

$F(Vz, Uz, \alpha t) \geq$

$\max. \{ F(Vz, USz, t), F(Vz, Uz, t), F(Vz, Uz, t), F(Vz, Uz, t),$

$F(Vz, Sz, t),$

$F(Vz, Uz, t), F(Vz, Uz, t), F(Vz, Uz, t), F(Vz, Uz, t),$

$F(Vz, Uz, t)\}$

$F(Vz, Uz, \alpha t) \geq F(Vz, Uz, t)$

$Vz = Uz$.

$F(Vz, z, \alpha t) \geq F(Vz, z, t)$

$Vz = z$. Such that $Vz = Uz = z$. (12)

Let $x = \beta x_{20n}$, and $y = \delta x_{20n-1}$,
(iii) and (iv) we have

$$\begin{aligned} & f\beta x_{20n}, A\beta x_{20n}, C\beta x_{20n}, H\beta x_{20n}, J\beta x_{20n}, L\beta x_{20n} \\ & N\beta x_{20n}, Q\beta x_{20n}, S\beta x_{20n}, U\beta x_{20n}, \delta\beta x_{20n} \rightarrow \beta z, \\ & g\delta x_{20n-1}, B\delta x_{20n-1}, D\delta x_{20n-1}, I\delta x_{20n-1}, K\delta x_{20n-1}, M\delta x_{20n-1}, \\ & P\delta x_{20n-1}, R\delta x_{20n-1}, T\delta x_{20n-1}, V\delta x_{20n-1} \\ & , \beta\delta x_{20n-1} \rightarrow \delta z \\ & F(f\beta x_{20n}, g\delta x_{20n-1}, \alpha t) \geq \\ & \max. \{ F(A\beta x_{20n}, B\delta x_{20n-1}, t), \\ & F(C\beta x_{20n}, D\delta x_{20n-1}, t), \\ & F(H\beta x_{20n}, I\delta x_{20n-1}, t), F(J\beta x_{20n}, K\delta x_{20n-1}, t), \\ & F(L\beta x_{20n}, M\delta x_{20n-1}, t), F(N\beta x_{20n}, P\delta x_{20n-1}, t), \\ & F(Q\beta x_{20n}, R\delta x_{20n-1}, t), \\ & (S\beta x_{20n}, T\delta x_{20n-1}, t), F(U\beta x_{20n}, V\delta x_{20n-1}, t), \\ & F(\delta\beta x_{20n}, \beta\delta x_{20n-1}, t) \} \text{ as } n \rightarrow \infty \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & F(\beta z, \delta z, \alpha t) \geq \\ & \max. \{ F(\beta z, \delta z, t), F(\beta z, \delta z, t), F(\beta z, \delta z, t), F(\beta z, \delta z, t) \\ & F(\beta z, \delta z, t), \\ & F(\beta z, \delta z, t), \\ & F(\beta z, \delta z, \alpha t) \geq F(\beta z, \delta z, t) \end{aligned}$$

$$\beta z = \delta z .$$

$$F(\beta z, z, \alpha t) \geq F(\beta z, z, t)$$

$$\beta z = z. \text{ Such that } \beta z = \delta z = z. \text{ (13)}$$

Such that equations (4) to (13) we have

$$\begin{aligned} & Az = Bz = Cz = Dz = Hz = Iz = Jz = Kz = Lz = \\ & Mz = Nz = Pz = Qz = Rz = Sz = Tz = Uz = Vz = \\ & \delta z = \beta z = z. \quad (14) \end{aligned}$$

Let $x = gx_{20n-19}$, and $y = fx_{20n-20}$,
(iii) and (iv) we have

$$\begin{aligned} & fgx_{20n-19}, Agx_{20n-19}, Cgx_{20n-19}, Hgx_{20n-19}, Jgx_{20n-19}, Lgx_{20n-19}, \\ & Ngx_{20n-19}, Qgx_{20n-19}, Sgx_{20n-19}, Ugx_{20n-19}, \delta gx_{20n-19} \\ & \rightarrow gz, \\ & gfx_{20n-20}, Bfx_{20n-20}, Dfx_{20n-20}, Ifx_{20n-20}, \\ & Kfx_{20n-20}, Mfx_{20n-20} \\ & Pfx_{20n-20}, Rfx_{20n-20}, Tfx_{20n-20}, Vfx_{20n-20}, \beta fx_{20n-20} \\ & \rightarrow fz \\ & F(fgx_{20n-19}, gfx_{18n-18}, \alpha t) \geq \\ & \max. \{ F(Agx_{20n-19}, Bfx_{18n-18}, t), \\ & F(Cgx_{20n-19}, Dfx_{18n-18}, t), \\ & F(Hgx_{20n-19}, Ifx_{18n-18}, t), \\ & F(Jgx_{20n-19}, Kfx_{18n-18}, t), \\ & F(Lgx_{20n-19}, Mfx_{18n-18}, t), \\ & F(Ngx_{20n-19}, Pfx_{18n-18}, t), \\ & F(Qgx_{20n-19}, Rfx_{18n-18}, t), \\ & (Sgx_{20n-19}, Tfx_{18n-18}, t), F(Ugx_{20n-19}, Vfx_{18n-18}, t) \\ & , F(Ugx_{20n-19}, Vfx_{18n-18}, t) \} \text{ as } n \rightarrow \infty \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & F(gz, fz, \alpha t) \geq \\ & \max. \{ F(gz, fz, t), F(gz, fz, t), F(gz, fz, t), F(gz, fz, t), \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & F(gz, fz, t), \\ & F(gz, fz, t), F(gz, fz, t), F(gz, fz, t), F(gz, fz, t), \\ & F(gz, fz, t) \} \end{aligned}$$

$$M(gz, fz, \alpha t) \geq M(gz, fz, t)$$

$$\begin{aligned} & F(gz, z, \alpha t) \geq F(gz, z, t) \\ & gz = z. \text{ Such that } gz = fz = z. \text{ (15)} \end{aligned}$$

By (14) and (15).

$$\begin{aligned} & fz = gz = Az = Bz = Cz = Dz = Hz = Iz = Jz = \\ & Kz = Lz = Mz = Nz = Pz = Qz = Rz = Sz = Tz = \\ & Vz = Uz = \delta z = \beta z = z. \text{ Hence } z \text{ is common fixed} \\ & \text{point of} \\ & f, g, A, B, C, D, H, I, J, K, L, M, N, P, Q, R, S, T, U, V, \delta \text{ and } \beta. \end{aligned}$$

Case II: let w be another common fixed point, also
 $z \neq w$ we have $x = z, y = w$ by (iv),

$$\begin{aligned} & F(fz, gw, \alpha t) \\ & \geq \max. \{ F(Az, Bw, t), F(Cz, Dw, t), F(Hz, Iw, t), F(Jz, Kw, t), \\ & F(Lz, Mw, t), F(Nz, Pw, t), F(Qz, Rw, t), F(Sz, Tw, t), \\ & F(Uz, Vw, t), F(\delta z, \beta w, t) \} \text{ as } n \rightarrow \infty \\ & F(z, w, \alpha t) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \geq \max. \{ F(z, w, t), \\ & F(z, w, t), F(z, w, t), F(z, w, t), F(z, w, t), F(z, w, t) \} \\ & F(z, w, \alpha t) \geq F(z, w, t). \text{ Hence we have,} \\ & z = w \text{ which is contradict and } z \text{ is a unique common} \\ & \text{fixed point of self mappings} \\ & f, g, A, B, C, D, H, I, J, K, L, M, N, P, Q, R, S, T, U, V, \delta \text{ and } \beta. \end{aligned}$$

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